

Unequal Classrooms: The Joint Effects of Ability Peer Effect and Socioeconomic Composition on Academic Track Enrollment

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Abstract

The effects of peer abilities in education are central to understanding how the individual educational pathway is shaped by social environments. Although traditional theories emphasize positive spillovers from high-achieving peers, alternative perspectives such as social contrast hypotheses highlight potential negative consequences for student motivation and self-concept. In addition, much attention has been devoted to the important role of parental socioeconomic background, but less attention has been paid to its interaction with ability-peer effects. This study aims to investigate how the effects of peer ability and the socioeconomic composition of classmates influence the enrollment of students on the path to university when they switch to lower secondary schools in Italy. The results show that the effect of peer ability is negative, but the socioeconomic composition of the classroom plays a compensatory role.

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Data Access

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1 Introduction

The learning environment plays a crucial role in shaping students' cognitive and socio-emotional development, ultimately influencing their educational transitions and acquired competences. From a pedagogical perspective, interactions within the learning environment are central to the formation of self-concept and peer understanding. A diverse classroom composition fosters both personal growth and social integration, allowing students to learn from one another and to internalize common behavioral norms.

Since the post-war period—and particularly following the civil rights movements of the 1960s in the United States and Europe—educational policies have been progressively oriented toward desegregation. Governments gradually dismantled segregated schools and classrooms and, in several cases, enacted laws prohibiting biased student sorting based on socioeconomic background or ethnicity. This process also affected ability-based grouping. Whereas sorting by prior achievement was once widespread, contemporary education systems have moved toward either early or late tracking, or have largely avoided ability-based grouping altogether, particularly in primary and lower-secondary education.

The underlying rationale is that greater diversity enhances cognitive and socioemotional development: By interacting with peers of different abilities, students learn from one another and emulate high-achieving classmates who set aspirational social norms. This mechanism of **assimilation** has been widely documented in the literature. Yet, this is only one side of the story. The other side, often overlooked, concerns the possibility that social comparison operates in the opposite direction. Being surrounded by high-achieving peers can sometimes be discouraging, activating a **social contrast** or “**big-fish-in-little-pond**” mechanism: students begin to perceive themselves as less competent relative to their peers, which can reduce motivation and investment in schoolwork.

A further dimension that remains conceptually underdeveloped is the **socioeconomic composition** of the classroom. Parental education and social background may operate through **parental peer effects**, whereby students indirectly benefit from the involvement, expectations, and informational resources of more educated parents. Such parents often monitor instruction more closely, engage actively with teachers, and foster a more

stimulating learning environment both inside and outside the classroom. Previous studies have shown that these processes can raise collective educational aspirations and improve academic outcomes.

Despite extensive research, there is still no clear consensus on how **ability-related peer effects** operate, nor on how they interact with **socioeconomic peer effects**. It remains uncertain whether positive emulation mechanisms dominate, or whether negative contrast effects prevail, and whether socioeconomic advantages among peers can compensate for or amplify ability-related disparities. These uncertainties reflect not only theoretical gaps, but also empirical limitations, particularly the lack of causal designs that can disentangle the multiple intertwined peer influences in education.

This study contributes to filling this gap by developing a unified framework that jointly examines the effects of ability and socioeconomic peer composition. We combine a theoretical discussion of mechanisms of **emulation versus social contrast** with a causal research design that credibly identifies peer effects by exploiting longitudinal administrative data from Italy. Italy represents a particularly relevant case: It is a highly developed country with **low social mobility** and **limited educational investment**, where families play a decisive role in shaping the educational pathways of children. The centralized nature of the Italian education system ensures uniform rules across schools and, crucially, the transition from primary to lower secondary education involves a quasi-random reshuffling of students across classes. These institutional features, together with comprehensive administrative records, provide a rare opportunity to investigate peer effects while minimizing bias from reflection or selection.

Our findings suggest that exposure to peers with higher achievement tends to activate a **social contrast mechanism**, leading to modest but systematic negative effects on track placement once prior achievement is controlled. In contrast, the **socioeconomic composition** of the classroom exerts consistently positive effects, compensating - at least in part - for the negative influence of peer exposure based on ability.

2 Theoretical frame

When examining two strands of literature—those on ability peer effects and on socioeconomic composition, both of which focus on dynamics within the learning environment—it becomes evident that they often fail to communicate with each other. This disconnect represents a missed opportunity for theoretical complementarity, with important implications for research design. The emphasis on the effects of the ability of the peers is particularly relevant: Since Coleman’s seminal work, this perspective has been central to debates on how to desegregate schools and improve classroom diversity. However, only a few studies have jointly considered other key classroom characteristics, such as socioeconomic composition, despite their equally significant influence.

This need for complementarity is crucial from a policy perspective. On the one hand, policymakers often invest in promoting ability diversity, but such efforts may backfire if social contrast mechanisms prevail, potentially leading to lower motivation and performance among some students. As a result, there may be a temptation to create more homogeneous classes to reduce these effects and facilitate more targeted teaching. However, this reasoning overlooks the fact that ability homogeneity often implies socioeconomic homogeneity as well, since higher socioeconomic status is typically associated with higher competency levels.

For this reason, it is essential to study the ability effects of the peer and the socioeconomic composition together within a coherent research design, to assess whether the two follow a cumulative pattern in the same direction or overlap in complex ways. Against this backdrop, an important yet underexplored question arises: How do peer effects related to both ability and socioeconomic background jointly shape student achievement?

Although existing studies have often examined these dimensions separately, few have investigated their simultaneous operation and potential interaction within the same analytical framework. This gap is striking, given that ability and socioeconomic status are deeply intertwined in shaping students’ opportunities to learn, their access to resources, and their positioning within classroom hierarchies.

Our study contributes to filling this void by jointly analyzing ability- and SES-related

peer effects, thereby capturing how cognitive and social resources coexist and either reinforce or offset each other in shaping achievement. We focus on whether the average ability exposure of peers and the socioeconomic background of the classroom produce distinct or interacting effects. In doing so, our goal is to clarify whether ability and social background constitute complementary or competing mechanisms of peer influence.

3 Literature review

3.1 Ability peer effects

Peer effects in education are often explained through skill complementarities and spillovers: high-achieving students may enhance classroom learning by setting positive examples and increasing instructional efficiency, while low-performing or disruptive students can hinder learning by diverting attention and reducing classroom cohesion (Lazear, 2001; Epple and Romano, 1998). Social learning theory (Bandura, 1977) suggests that students adopt behaviors - both positive and negative - through observation and imitation. High-achieving peers can inspire each other to work hard and improve their grades (Gong et al., 2019), while subcultural and labeling theories suggest that peer groups can also reinforce anti-school attitudes (Willis, 1977; Becker, 1963).

However, the theory of social comparison (Festinger, 1954) suggests that comparison can take multiple forms and that exposure to high-achieving peers is not necessarily beneficial. In contrast, contrasting comparisons may lower self-esteem and reduce engagement, especially for students with lower performance. This process is closely related to the well-documented *Frog Pond Effect* (Davis, 1966), which posits that an individual's self-evaluation depends not only on their absolute performance, but also on their relative standing within their reference group (Jonsson and Mood, 2008; Rosenqvist, 2018). For example, a student with above average ability may feel less competent if surrounded by exceptionally high-achieving peers, whereas the same student might feel more confident and motivated in a lower-achieving context. These dynamics are particularly salient during adolescence, a period marked by heightened sensitivity to peer evaluation and identity

formation (Alexander and Campbell, 1964).

In general, the literature on peer effects features a theoretical contradiction between normative models - predicting positive spillover effects from high-ability peers (Goldsmith, 2011; Jencks and Mayer, 1990; Legewie and DiPrete, 2012) - and social contrast theories such as the “frog pond” perspective (Marsh, 1987; Rosenqvist, 2018), which propose that high-achieving peers can undermine students’ self-confidence and, ultimately, their performance.

A large body of research examining how peers’ ability levels influence student achievement estimates the effects of the *average* ability level among peers (i.e., linear-in-means models). This literature yields highly mixed results. Although some studies find positive and significant effects of average peer achievement on students’ own achievement (e.g., Hoxby, 2000; Boozer and Cacciola, 2001; Hanushek et al., 2003; Betts and Zau, 2004; Hoxby and Weingarh, 2006; Vigdor, 2006; Vigdor and Nechyba, 2007; Ammermueller and Pischke, 2009; Carman and Zhang, 2012; Lavy et al., 2012), others report small or null effects (e.g., Angrist and Lang, 2004; Lefgren, 2004; Lavy et al., 2012b; Imberman et al., 2012; Burke and Sass, 2013). Still, other studies find negative effects on both academic achievement and educational choices in distinct national contexts, such as Sweden (Jonsson and Mood, 2008) and the United States (Antecol et al., 2016). All these studies overlook the complementarity with socioeconomic background, whose underlying mechanisms we now discuss.

3.2 Socioeconomic composition effect

When examining socioeconomic composition, scholars often refer to the various mechanisms that may underlie the presence of families from higher socioeconomic backgrounds, as well as the effects that can operate at the classroom level.

Direct enrichment and learning norms are perhaps the most immediate channel. Children whose parents have higher education levels tend to bring richer vocabulary, more structured learning habits, and greater cultural capital to the classroom. These characteristics can raise the overall cognitive environment, setting higher academic standards, and

stimulating participation among peers. The influence of these children is not limited to individual interactions, but extends to collective learning processes, since shared classroom activities provide occasions for imitation and mutual reinforcement of learning-oriented behaviors.

Closely related to this process is the role of **the environment of the classroom and the behavioral norms**. Higher education parents often foster attitudes of diligence, punctuality, and cooperation in their children. When these children form a larger share of the classroom, they help shape a more orderly and academically focused atmosphere, reducing disturbances and enhancing the effectiveness of teaching (Fruehwirth and Gagete-Miranda, 2019). In turn, this improved climate interacts with the responses of teachers, leading to the next mechanism.

Teacher response and instructional adaptation reflect how teachers adjust their effort and pedagogical strategies in the presence of highly educated parents. Teachers may perceive these parents as more engaged, informed, or demanding, and therefore respond with increased instructional rigor, more personalized feedback, or greater attention to literacy and other foundational skills (Dufflo et al., 2011; Jackson, 2016). This adjustment in teacher behavior amplifies the learning environment, benefiting all students, though potentially widening disparities if teachers allocate attention unevenly.

A related but more socially mediated channel involves **parental involvement spillovers**. Parents with higher education levels often model active participation in school life communicating effectively with teachers, volunteering in classroom activities, or mobilizing resources for the school community. Such practices can diffuse informally to other parents, encouraging a culture of collective engagement and accountability that raises expectations and learning opportunities for all children.

At the same time, **the informational and signaling mechanisms** operate through interactions between parents and teachers. Educated parents tend to exchange information about effective learning strategies, extracurricular opportunities, or the relative quality of teachers. This information circulation can improve the overall flow of educational knowledge between families. Furthermore, teachers may interpret a classroom with a

higher proportion of educated parents as a signal of higher collective potential, which can influence their grading standards, grouping decisions, and curriculum pacing.

These processes are intertwined with **relative performance and motivational responses**. In early education, when skill differences are easily observable, parents often compare the progress of their children with that of their classmates. Exposure to children of highly educated parents can push some families to increase their own investments and engagement, while others, perceiving their children as lagging behind, can reduce or withdraw their efforts. This dynamic can generate positive and negative externalities within the same classroom, reinforcing inequality through differentiated motivational responses.

Finally, these various mechanisms can be complemented by **unobserved complementary skills** caused by children of highly educated parents. Such peers may possess socio-emotional attributes, such as self-regulation, persistence, or verbal confidence, that are not fully captured by academic assessments but interact with teaching practices to improve learning for everyone Fruehwirth and Gagete-Miranda (2019).

In sum, peer parental education can influence student outcomes through an intricate combination of cognitive, social, and institutional channels. Direct enrichment processes shape learning norms, which in turn affect classroom climate and teacher responses. These dynamics are further reinforced by parental spillovers, information exchange, and relative performance effects, all of which operate simultaneously. Understanding how these mechanisms interact is crucial to identifying whether parental education between peers functions primarily as *resource amplifier*, *normative model*, or *redistributive force* in early educational contexts.

4 Analytical strategy

4.1 Data and variables

For both countries, we use administrative data on the educational trajectories of students. For Italy, access is provided by INVALSI, the Italian National Institute for the Evaluation

of the Education System. To ensure cross-country comparability, we follow three student cohorts enrolled in Grade 5 during the school years 2012 / 2013 and 2013 / 2014 and tracked them for three subsequent years, up to Grade 8. This design allows us to use Grade 5 test scores as both a pre-peer exposure control and as the baseline to build the reference group prior to the formation of new peer groups in the lower secondary school.

Track enrollment is measured after grade Grade 8 and is a dummy 0 non-academic track and 1 academic track. All test scores are standardized within each cohort to have mean 0 and standard deviation 1. At the individual level, we observe variables such as gender, parental education, and background of migration. Gender is coded as 1 for females and 0 for males. Migration background distinguishes between native students and first- or second-generation immigrants. Parental education is coded as 1 when at least one parent has tertiary education.

To capture peer effects, we construct indicators of peer composition based on two key dimensions: academic achievement prior and socioeconomic background (ESCS). Both measures are computed at the classroom level using a 'leave one out' procedure that excludes the focal student from the average, thus avoiding mechanical reflection bias. Formally, the average peer achievement for student i in school s , cohort k , and year $t - 1$ is defined as follows:

$$\overline{TestScore}_{skt-1}^{(-i)} = \frac{1}{N_{sk}^S - 1} \sum_{j \in G_{sk}^S, j \neq i} TestScore_{j,t-1}, \quad (1)$$

where G_{sk}^S is the set of all peers in the same school and cohort, and N_{sk}^S its size.

Analogously, we compute the **average peer socioeconomic status** as:

$$\overline{ESCS}_{skt-1}^{(-i)} = \frac{1}{N_{sk}^S - 1} \sum_{j \in G_{sk}^S, j \neq i} ESCS_{j,t-1}, \quad (2)$$

where $ESCS_{j,t-1}$ denotes the standardized socioeconomic index of student j , based on parental education, occupational status, and household resources collected in the INVALSI student background questionnaire.

Both peer variables are cohort-standardized to ensure comparability over years and to

eliminate any cohort-specific scaling differences. Anchoring these indicators in Grade 5 data—prior to lower-secondary school entry—ensures that they capture pretreatment characteristics that are unaffected by the subsequent peer environment. This characteristic strengthens causal interpretability, since peer exposure in Grade 8 is conditioned on information measured before the re-sorting of students into new classes.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of key variables

Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Track	0.576		0.000	1.000
Average ability	0.085	0.905	-10.079	5.325
Average ESCS	0.018	0.911	-6.215	4.059
Test 5th grade	0.039	0.967	-5.805	4.528
ESCS	0.096	0.991	-3.111	2.600
Gender	0.508		0.000	1.000
Migration background	0.085		0.000	1.000
Share of females	0.507	0.124	0.000	1.000
Share of migrants	0.088	0.114	0.000	1.000

We compute these peer measures for the full set of classmates, and in robustness checks also by gender (e.g., mean ability of male vs. female peers). Taken together, these measures provide complementary lenses on two central mechanisms of peer influence: one operating through **academic ability spillovers**—reflecting the informational and motivational effects of exposure to more skilled peers - and the other through **socioeconomic composition**—capturing normative and resource-based channels that shape classroom climate and learning opportunities.

4.2 Empirical strategy

Our empirical strategy identifies the effects of the peers by exploiting the variation in the average composition of cohorts that enter the same school over time, following the intuition of Hoxby (2000). Even within the same school, different cohorts display heterogeneous average levels of both academic achievement and socioeconomic composition. We leverage this within-school, across-cohort variation to identify the causal effect of peer exposure on subsequent student performance.

We estimate the following value-added specification with school and cohort fixed effects:

$$Y_{i,s,k,t+3} = \alpha + \beta_1 \tau_{i,s,k,t_0} + \beta_2 \overline{Ability}_{s,k,t_0}^{(-i)} + \beta_3 \overline{ESCS}_{s,k,t_0}^{(-i)} + \beta_4 X_{i,s,k,t_0} + \delta_s + \gamma_k + \varepsilon_{i,s,k,t_0} \quad (3)$$

where $Y_{i,s,k,t+3}$ denotes student i 's track enrollment in high school after Grade 8, τ_{i,s,k,t_0} represents prior individual achievement in Grade 5 (pre-treatment stage), $\overline{Ability}_{s,k,t_0}^{(-i)}$ is the 'leave one out' average of the peer test scores (mean of classmates excluding i) and $\overline{ESCS}_{s,k,t_0}^{(-i)}$ is the corresponding 'leave one out' average of the socioeconomic background of the peer. The vector X_{i,s,k,t_0} includes individual and family controls (sex, parental education, migration background), while δ_s and γ_k are fixed effects for school and cohorts, respectively. The error term ε_{i,s,k,t_0} captures idiosyncratic unobservables.

This formulation allows us to estimate the separate and joint effects of peer ability and peer socioeconomic composition on later achievement. By including both peer measures simultaneously, we can assess whether the apparent influence of peer achievement reflects pure cognitive spillovers, socioeconomic contextual effects, or both. Because the peer variables are measured prior to the formation of new peer groups (at Grade 5), they are predetermined with respect to the outcome and unaffected by subsequent sorting or co-movement within classrooms.

Identification The inclusion of school-fixed effects ensures that identification relies solely on variation across cohorts within the same school, effectively comparing successive student cohorts exposed to slightly different classroom peer compositions. This design eliminates any time-invariant confounders at the school level, such as teacher quality, infrastructure, or demographics of the catchment area. The fixed effects of the cohort, in turn, absorb aggregate shocks or nationwide changes in educational policy or testing environments.

Addressing identification challenges. Estimating peer effects poses several well-known challenges: reflection, selection bias, and confounding (Manski, 1993). We mitigate each as follows.

Reflection. By defining peer measures based on pre-exposure variables (Grade 5 test scores and ESCS) and outcomes three years later (Grade 8), we eliminate simultaneity and mechanical feedback. Peer averages are constructed using a “leave-one-out” design, ensuring that an individual’s own characteristics do not directly affect the peer variable.

Selection bias. School fixed effects rule out unobserved, time-invariant heterogeneity across schools, while the longitudinal design -tracking multiple cohorts -neutralizes selection into schools, provided such selection remains stable over time. Thus, estimates are based on fluctuations within the school between classrooms in cohort composition, rather than differences between schools.

Confounding. We include lagged individual achievement and a set of demographic covariates (X_{i,s,k,t_0}) to control for preexisting differences between students. The model therefore mimics as a specification *value-added*, where the most persistent un-observables that affect learning are captured by the previous performance of the test.

Interpretation. The coefficients β_2 and β_3 capture distinct but potentially complementary mechanisms of peer influence. A positive β_2 would suggest that exposure to peers with higher levels of achievement enhances learning through academic spillovers and classroom norms of effort, while $\beta_3 > 0$ would indicate that the socioeconomic composition of peers exerts independent effects - through cultural capital, expectations, or parental involvement. Comparing their magnitudes allows us to assess whether achievement-based or socioeconomic sorting plays a larger role in shaping educational outcomes.

Overall, this design leverages administrative microdata, predetermined peer variables, and fixed-effects estimation to identify credible estimates of the effects of both ability- and SES-related peer composition on student performance.

5 A permutation–mixture framework to detect within-school sorting

To identify whether schools systematically sort students across classes according to ability or socioeconomic background, we develop a two-stage analytical framework that combines model-based and design-based reasoning. The procedure, implemented on administrative microdata, quantifies the extent to which the internal composition of each school deviates from what would be expected under random assignment of students to classes.

In the first stage, we compute a school-level measure of concentration for each dimension of interest, achievement and socioeconomic background. The key idea is to evaluate whether certain traits are unevenly distributed across classes within the same school. For each school, the observed distribution is compared to a large number of hypothetical random allocations, obtained by repeatedly permuting student–classroom assignments while keeping the overall composition of the school constant. The resulting statistic can be interpreted as the proportion of random allocations that produce a concentration equal to or higher than the observed one. Values close to zero indicate a random-like distribution of students, while values approaching one suggest that students are more clustered by ability or background than would occur by chance. This permutation-based comparison ensures that each school is evaluated against its own feasible counterfactual, rather than against an external benchmark.

Because sorting may occur on both academic and social dimensions, we then synthesize the two pieces of evidence into a single summary indicator. Several aggregation rules are possible, but in the main specification we classify a school as potentially non-compliant if it displays strong concentration in either dimension. Alternative combinations, including Fisher-style aggregation and weighted averages, are tested for robustness. Schools with fewer than two classes are automatically treated as compliant, since concentration cannot be defined when there is only one group.

In the second stage, we transform the continuous evidence of sorting into an operational classification using a probabilistic mixture model. The logic is that, in all schools, the

empirical distribution of the concentration index reflects two latent groups: one composed of schools whose classroom composition is consistent with random assignment (the 'compliant' group) and another of schools exhibiting stronger than random clustering (the 'non-compliant' group). To separate these two components, we fit a Gaussian mixture model that estimates the typical behavior of each group and computes, for every school, the posterior probability of being non-compliant. Schools that exceed a predefined probability threshold are marked as displaying potential within-school sorting.

This probabilistic approach has several advantages. It allows for uncertainty in the classification, avoids arbitrary cut-offs, and adapts to the empirical distribution of the data. Furthermore, the framework can be transparently audited: the relationship between the chosen probability threshold and the underlying evidence statistic can be visualized through histograms showing where schools fall along the compliance spectrum.

Several design features strengthen the robustness and interpretability of the procedure. All reference distributions are constructed within schools, ensuring that the assessment is not affected by heterogeneity between schools. The method requires a minimal number of classes for eligibility, but otherwise retains all schools in the dataset by marking single-classroom institutions as compliant. Input variables are scaled and numerically stabilized to prevent outliers or near-constant distributions from distorting results. Each step of the computation is reproducible, checked and saved independently, making the procedure suitable for large-scale administrative data and for replication by external researchers.

The algorithm yields three families of outputs. First, for each school, it produces indicators of concentration for achievement and socioeconomic background, their combined score, and the estimated probability of noncompliance. Second, it provides diagnostics of the fitted mixture model, including fit and decision threshold measures. Third, it produces visual summaries that help interpret how schools are distributed across the compliance spectrum. Moreover, schools with concentration indices around 0.5 exhibit allocations consistent with randomness, while those with values near one display pronounced clustering of students by ability or background. The probabilistic classification thus integrates a design-based benchmark (from within-school permutations) with a model-based calibration

(from cross-school mixtures), achieving a balance between statistical rigor and policy interpretability.

Figure 1: Sorting test

About 15% of schools are identified as non-random sorters according to our test. The schools excluded from our analytical sample fall into two categories: those with only one class, which therefore provide no within-school variation to exploit, and those that do not properly randomize students across classes. For both types, we apply Inverse Probability Weighting (IPW) and store the resulting weights, which are then used to weight our estimates in order to recover full representativeness of the school population. The schools that are not included in our sample fall into two categories: schools with only one class, which therefore provide no within-school variation to exploit, and schools that do not properly randomize students across classes. For both types, we apply Inverse Probability Weighting (IPW) and store the resulting weights, which are then used to weight our estimates in order to recover full representativeness of the school population.

6 Results

6.1 Descriptive evidence: classroom composition

This section provides a descriptive overview of the composition of the classroom in two key dimensions, mean academic ability and socioeconomic status (ESCS), and of their joint distribution. These descriptive patterns offer preliminary insight into how peer environments vary across cohorts, providing the empirical background for the identification

strategy developed in the next section.

Figure 2 displays the distribution of the ability at the classroom level in two consecutive cohorts. The histogram reveals a strongly normal and symmetric shape.

Figure 2: Distribution of classroom ability by cohort (overlaid histograms)

Turning to socioeconomic composition, Figure 3 shows the corresponding distribution of average classroom ESCS. The pattern is again quite normal, mirroring that of ability.

The joint pattern of ability and ESCS is illustrated in Figure 4, which plots a hexbin heat map of the two variables at the classroom level. The dense elliptical core, positively sloped along the 45-degree line, reveals a moderate but clear correlation between the two dimensions: classrooms with higher socioeconomic backgrounds tend also to display higher average achievement, but the overall correlation is quite low as 0.25. This association is theoretically consistent with the idea that family resources reinforce both cognitive preparation and the overall learning climate. From an empirical point of view, it emphasizes the importance of considering the ability and socioeconomic composition together, as omitting one dimension could lead to an overestimation of the influence of the other. The compact concentration of observations around the center, combined with thinner, low-density peripheries, suggests limited though non-negligible within-school segregation, meaning that while highly advantaged and disadvantaged classes exist, they remain

Figure 3: Distribution of classroom ESCS by cohort (overlaid histograms)

Figure 4: Hexbin heatmap of classroom ability and socioeconomic composition

exceptions rather than the norm.

Together, these visual patterns convey three substantive messages. First, the strong temporal stability of both classroom ability and ESCS supports the validity of exploiting within-school, across-cohort variation to identify peer effects. Second, the positive association between the two dimensions underscores that socioeconomic and ability-related peer mechanisms are intertwined: cognitive spillovers are likely to be complemented or mediated by social and normative influences shaped by the socioeconomic profile of the classroom. Third, the limited dispersion observed in the tails suggests that while extreme classes exist, the Italian lower-secondary system largely operates within a relatively narrow compositional range, consistent with partial but not pervasive stratification.

6.2 Main regression results

Table 2 reports the estimates of six regression models examining how peer **ability** and **socioeconomic composition (ESCS)** jointly shape the track enrollment. All models include individual controls, school fixed effects, and robust standard errors clustered at the school level. Models 1 and 2 estimate the effect of average peer ability; Models 3 and 4 include the socioeconomic composition of peers; Models 5 and 6 combine both dimensions.

The empirical results presented in Table 2 show that peer composition significantly shapes track enrollment, though through distinct and partly offset mechanisms. The coefficient on **average peer ability** is positive and significant in the bivariate specification, but becomes slightly negative once the prior achievement is included, indicating that the raw association mainly reflects selection rather than genuine spillovers. In contrast, **average peer socioeconomic status (ESCS)** exhibits consistently positive effects across specifications, suggesting that the social and cultural resources embedded in the composition of the classroom exert a strong influence on learning outcomes even after controlling for individual background and prior performance. Individual-level differences remain pronounced: girls outperform boys by about 0.24 percentage points, while first- and second-generation immigrant students achieve lower scores, although these gaps narrow once peer and school effects are considered.

Table 2: Regression results – Peer Ability and Socioeconomic Composition

	Average Ability	+ Ability	Average ESCS	+ ESCS	+ Ability	+ Average Ability
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
Average Ability	0.00** (0.00)	-0.03*** (0.00)				-0.03*** (0.00)
Average ESCS			0.03*** (0.00)	0.01*** (0.00)	0.02*** (0.00)	0.01*** (0.00)
Test 5 th grade		0.14*** (0.00)			0.12*** (0.00)	0.11*** (0.00)
Socioeconomic background				0.13*** (0.00)	0.11*** (0.00)	0.11*** (0.00)
Share of Females	0.01 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)	0.00 (0.01)	0.00 (0.01)	0.00 (0.01)
Share of Non-Natives	-0.01 (0.01)	-0.05*** (0.01)	0.02* (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)	-0.02* (0.01)	-0.00 (0.01)
Girls	0.25*** (0.00)	0.25*** (0.00)	0.25*** (0.00)	0.25*** (0.00)	0.25*** (0.00)	0.25*** (0.00)
Immigrant	-0.15*** (0.00)	-0.09*** (0.00)	-0.15*** (0.00)	-0.07*** (0.00)	-0.03*** (0.00)	-0.03*** (0.00)
Constant	0.44*** (0.00)	0.43*** (0.00)	0.43*** (0.00)	0.42*** (0.00)	0.42*** (0.00)	0.41*** (0.00)
Observations	405,570	405,570	405,570	405,570	405,570	405,570
R ²	0.15	0.22	0.16	0.21	0.26	0.26
Controls	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
School FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Source: INVALSI. Standard errors in parentheses.
 * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001.

Together, these results indicate that the learning environment functions not only as a space for cognitive development, but also as a social field in which norms, expectations, and comparisons operate simultaneously. The negative change in the coefficient of peer ability once prior achievement is controlled suggests the presence of mechanisms *social contrast*: therefore, exposure to high-achieving peers can undermine self-concept or perceived competence among lower-performing students. At the same time, the persistent positive association with peer ESCS supports the idea of *normative spillovers*, consistent with classrooms where children of more educated parents contribute to a learning-oriented environment through behavioral modeling, parental engagement, and teacher responsiveness. Hence, ability and socioeconomic composition seem to operate on complementary planes: while the former can generate competitive pressures, the latter fosters shared norms and collective resources that enhance learning.

These findings align with the larger theoretical tension between the dynamics of *emulative* and *contrastive* peers identified in the literature. Normative spillovers from advantaged peers appear to co-exist with contrasting mechanisms that produce differential motivational responses. The coexistence of these effects highlights why studies often report inconsistent results: peer influence is multidimensional, conditional on both the type of compositional attribute and the social meaning attached to it. The diagnostic

evidence from our permutation–mixture framework reinforces this interpretation, revealing that a non-trivial share of schools exhibits within-school concentration along ability or socioeconomic lines unlikely to occur under random allocation. Such concentration patterns imply that part of what is interpreted as a ‘peer effect’ may, in fact, stem from systematic internal classifying, shaping exposure to different learning environments.

7 Discussion and Conclusion

From a policy perspective, the findings point to two key implications. First, since the average peer composition, particularly socioeconomic, is important for track enrollment, interventions that improve the baseline quality of the classroom environment (for instance, through cooperative learning programs, early literacy support, or teacher training in heterogeneous settings) could amplify positive spillovers. However, several limitations must be acknowledged. Although our value-added specification and fixed school effects mitigate many endogeneity concerns, residual selection due to time-varying shocks, such as changes in school leadership, teacher turnover, or funding, cannot be entirely ruled out. The reliance on standardized test scores, while ensuring comparability and pretreatment anchoring, also narrows the focus to cognitive outcomes, leaving out unobserved socio-emotional skills. Finally, the permutation–mixture classification remains diagnostic rather than causal: it identifies deviations from random allocation but does not infer intent or assess consequences directly.

Future research should extend this framework in three directions. First, by modeling the temporal dimension of peer exposure, whether the effects cumulate or fade in the grades, it would be possible to understand when and how classroom composition matters most. Second, moving beyond linear-in-means specifications to test for nonlinearities or thresholds could clarify whether peer effects are symmetric across the distribution of ability or socioeconomic status. Third, linking diagnostic measures of concentration within the school with administrative or behavioral responses -such as resource allocation, teacher assignment, or remedial interventions - would enable a more actionable understanding of how schools can transform compositional diversity into a motor of educational equity.

In conclusion, this study shows that the effects of peers in education are not monolithic, but are the result of the interplay of social, cognitive, and institutional processes. Although exposure to high-achieving peers can generate both opportunities and tensions, a socially advantaged peer environment consistently promotes learning and may buffer the negative motivational consequences of academic contrast. These results underscore the importance of considering both the cognitive and social dimensions of the composition of the classroom when designing policies that promote inclusive and effective learning environments.

This paper advances the literature on peer effects by integrating a design-based estimate of exposure to *average peer achievement and socioeconomic composition* with a transparent diagnostic of the allocation within the school. The joint lens on ability- and SES-related composition foregrounds how cognitive and social resources operate together in shaping learning environments, and how institutional rules can amplify or dampen these channels. The core empirical message suggests that the ability-peer effects trigger social contrast mechanisms, whereas socioeconomic composition compensates through other plausible mechanisms. From a policy point of view, the findings advocate for two complementary levers: strengthening the quality of the average classroom and monitoring classroom formation to avoid systematic concentration that undermines equity. Methodologically, the permutation–mixture framework offers a tractable and auditable tool for systems that wish to assess their own allocation patterns without strong modeling assumptions.

References

- Alexander, C. N., & Campbell, E. Q. (1964). Peer influences in educational environments. *Sociology of Education*, 37(4), 422–434.
- Ammermueller, A., & Pischke, J.-S. (2009). Peer effects in European primary schools: Evidence from PIRLS. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 27(3), 315–348.
- Angrist, J. D., & Lang, K. (2004). Does school integration generate peer effects? Evidence from Boston’s Metco Program. *American Economic Review*, 94(5), 1613–1634.

- Antecol, H., Eren, O., & Ozbeklik, S. (2016). Peer effects in disadvantaged primary schools: Evidence from a randomized experiment. *Journal of Human Resources*, 51(1), 95–132.
- Bandura, A. (1977). *Social Learning Theory*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Becker, H. S. (1963). *Outsiders: Studies in the Sociology of Deviance*. New York: Free Press.
- Betts, J. R., & Zau, A. C. (2004). Peer groups and academic achievement: Panel evidence from administrative data. *RAND Education Working Paper*.
- Boozer, M. A., & Cacciola, S. E. (2001). Inside the “black box” of project STAR: Estimation of peer effects using experimental data. *Yale University Economic Growth Center Discussion Paper*.
- Burke, M. A., & Sass, T. R. (2013). Classroom peer effects and student achievement. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 31(1), 51–82.
- Carman, K. G., & Zhang, L. (2012). Classroom peer effects and academic achievement: Evidence from a randomized experiment in China. *Economics of Education Review*, 31(3), 389–399.
- Davis, J. A. (1966). The campus as a frog pond: An application of the theory of relative deprivation to career decisions of college men. *American Journal of Sociology*, 72(1), 17–31.
- Duflo, E., Dupas, P., & Kremer, M. (2011). Peer effects, teacher incentives, and the impact of tracking: Evidence from a randomized evaluation in Kenya. *American Economic Review*, 101(5), 1739–1774.
- Epple, D., & Romano, R. E. (1998). Competition between private and public schools, vouchers, and peer-group effects. *American Economic Review*, 88(1), 33–62.
- Festinger, L. (1954). A theory of social comparison processes. *Human Relations*, 7(2), 117–140.

- Goldsmith, P. (2011). Coleman revisited: School segregation, peers, and achievement. *Sociology of Education*, 84(4), 311–335.
- Gong, J., Lu, Y., & Song, H. (2019). Peer effects and academic achievement: Evidence from a Chinese university. *China Economic Review*, 55, 1–14.
- Hanushek, E. A., Kain, J. F., Markman, J. M., & Rivkin, S. G. (2003). Does peer ability affect student achievement? *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 18(5), 527–544.
- Hoxby, C. M. (2000). Peer effects in the classroom: Learning from gender and race variation. *NBER Working Paper No. 7867*.
- Hoxby, C. M., & Weingarth, G. (2006). Taking race out of the equation: School reassignment and the structure of peer effects. *NBER Working Paper No. 7869*.
- Imberman, S. A., Kugler, A. D., & Sacerdote, B. (2012). Katrina’s children: Evidence on the structure of peer effects from hurricane evacuees. *American Economic Review*, 102(5), 2048–2082.
- Jackson, C. Kirabo (2016). “The Effect of Single-Sex Education on Test Scores, School Completion, Arrests, and Teen Motherhood: Evidence from School Transitions.” *NBER Working Paper No. 22222*. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w22222>.
- Jencks, C., & Mayer, S. (1990). The social consequences of growing up in a poor neighborhood. In L. Lynn & M. McGahey (Eds.), *Inner-city Poverty in the United States* (pp. 111–186). Washington, DC: National Academy Press.
- Jonsson, J. O., & Mood, C. (2008). Choice by contrast in Swedish schools: How peers’ achievement affects educational choice. *Social Forces*, 87(2), 741–765.
- Lavy, V., Paserman, M. D., & Schlosser, A. (2012). Inside the black box of ability peer effects: Evidence from variation in the proportion of low achievers in the classroom. *Economic Journal*, 122(559), 208–237.

- Lavy, V., Silva, O., & Weinhardt, F. (2012). The good, the bad, and the average: Evidence on the scale and nature of ability peer effects in schools. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 30(2), 367–414.
- Lazear, Edward P. (2001). “Educational Production.” *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 116(3), 777–803. <https://doi.org/10.1162/00335530152466232>.
- Legewie, J., & DiPrete, T. A. (2012). School context and the gender gap in educational achievement. *American Sociological Review*, 77(3), 463–485.
- Lefgren, L. (2004). Educational peer effects and the Chicago public schools. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 56(2), 169–191.
- Marsh, H. W. (1987). The big-fish–little-pond effect on academic self-concept. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 79(3), 280–295.
- Manski, C. F. (1993). Identification of endogenous social effects: The reflection problem. *Review of Economic Studies*, 60(3), 531–542.
- Fruehwirth, Jane Cooley and Jessica Gagete-Miranda (2019). “Your Peers’ Parents: Spillovers from Parental Education.” *Economics of Education Review*, 73, 101910. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econedurev.2019.101910>.
- Rosenqvist, E. (2018). The frog pond revisited: Relative standing and academic achievement in Swedish schools. *Sociology of Education*, 91(3), 211–229.
- Vigdor, J. L. (2006). Peer effects in North Carolina public schools. In H. F. Ladd & E. B. Fiske (Eds.), *Handbook of Education Economics*. Amsterdam: Elsevier.
- Vigdor, J. L., & Nechyba, T. J. (2007). Peer effects in elementary school: Learning from “apparent” random assignment. *Economic Inquiry*, 45(3), 421–446.
- Willis, P. (1977). *Learning to Labor: How Working Class Kids Get Working Class Jobs*. Farnborough: Saxon House.

8 APPENDIX: A permutation–mixture framework to detect within-school sorting

We develop a two–stage procedure to detect whether schools exhibit systematic sorting of students across classes along achievement and socio–economic background. The approach hinges on a school–level statistic that measures how concentrated a given trait is across classes compared to what would be expected under random allocation, and on a probabilistic classifier that maps this statistic into a compliance decision. The pipeline is implemented on administrative micro–data and is designed to be fully reproducible, numerically stable, and resilient to incomplete cases.

Let s index schools and c classes within a school. For each student i we consider two continuous variables: Grade–5 achievement (`test5`) and socio–economic background (`escs`). Each variable is centered and scaled within the analytic sample to remove arbitrary level and scale differences; to avoid degeneracy when the dispersion is zero or ill–conditioned, scaling falls back to mean–centering. Denote by x_{isc} a generic scaled score. Because our concentration statistic requires non–negative inputs, we shift scores by a constant so that the transformed $\tilde{x}_{isc} = x_{isc} - \min_{i,s,c} x_{isc} + \varepsilon$ is strictly positive, with a small $\varepsilon > 0$ for numerical safety.

For each school s and variable $v \in \{\text{test5}, \text{escs}\}$ we first compute an observed concentration index based on a normalized Herfindahl–Hirschman measure. Let $X_{sc} = \sum_{i \in (s,c)} \tilde{x}_{isc}$ be the classroom–level mass and $X_s = \sum_c X_{sc}$ the school total. Define the classroom shares $p_{sc} = X_{sc}/X_s$ and the raw Herfindahl $HHI_s = \sum_c p_{sc}^2$. Because HHI_s depends on the number of classes N_s , we apply the standard normalization

$$H_s = \frac{HHI_s - \frac{1}{N_s}}{1 - \frac{1}{N_s}} \in [0, 1],$$

so that $H_s = 0$ under perfect equalization across classes and $H_s \rightarrow 1$ when the trait is concentrated in a single classroom. This observed index is then benchmarked against its random–allocation distribution obtained by permuting classroom labels K times within school. Let $H_s^{(1)}, \dots, H_s^{(K)}$ be the permuted values; the school–level evidence statistic is

the right-tail permutation p -value

$$S_s^{(v)} = \frac{1 + \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbb{1}\{H_s \geq H_s^{(k)}\}}{K + 1},$$

interpretable as the fraction of random allocations that are at least as concentrated as observed. Large $S_s^{(v)}$ indicates stronger-than-random concentration (suggestive of sorting). For numerical robustness we clamp $S_s^{(v)}$ to the open interval $(0, 1)$ and apply a negligible jitter to avoid boundary artifacts in the subsequent mixture fit. The permutation stage is parallelized across schools with progress-aware checkpoints; results are cached to allow resuming long runs.

Because sorting may manifest on achievement, socio-economic composition, or both, we synthesize the two pieces of evidence into a single scalar for eligible schools (i.e., those with at least `MIN_CLASSES` distinct classes; by design, schools below the threshold are flagged compliant and carried forward with a neutral record). Let $S_s^{(1)}$ and $S_s^{(2)}$ denote the clamped permutation p -values for `test5` and `escs`, respectively. We consider several combining rules with the common monotonicity property that larger values connote stronger evidence of sorting. In the main specification we use the logical-maximum,

$$S_s^{\text{comb}} = \max\{S_s^{(1)}, S_s^{(2)}\},$$

which classifies a school as suspicious if *either* dimension exhibits anomalous concentration. Two alternatives are implemented for robustness. First, a Fisher-type combination that treats $(1 - S)$ as ordinary p -values,

$$T_s = -2 \sum_{v=1}^2 \log(1 - S_s^{(v)}), \quad p_s^{\text{Fisher}} = \Pr(\chi_4^2 \geq T_s), \quad S_s^{\text{comb}} = 1 - p_s^{\text{Fisher}},$$

thus preserving the “larger is stronger” scale while leveraging cross-dimension concordance. Second, a weighted mean $S_s^{\text{comb}} = \sum_v w_v S_s^{(v)}$ with user-specified w_v summing to one, which is useful when policy places differential emphasis on the two traits.

We convert the continuous S_s^{comb} into an operational binary decision via a Gaus-

sian–mixture classifier. The idea is that the empirical distribution of S^{comb} across schools is plausibly a mixture of a “compliant” group centered at lower values and a “non–compliant” group centered at higher values. We fit a k –component normal mixture to $\{S_s^{\text{comb}}\}_{s \in \mathcal{E}}$ (eligible schools),

$$f(S) = \sum_{j=1}^k \lambda_j \phi(S; \mu_j, \sigma_j^2),$$

by expectation–maximization with multiple random starts and convergence diagnostics; $k = 2$ is the default, while $k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ is compared via BIC for sensitivity. Let $j^* = \arg \max_j \mu_j$ index the high–mean component. For each school we compute the posterior membership probability $\pi_s = \Pr(\text{non–compliant} \mid S_s^{\text{comb}}) = \lambda_{j^*} \phi(S_s^{\text{comb}}; \mu_{j^*}, \sigma_{j^*}^2) / f(S_s^{\text{comb}})$ and classify as non–compliant when

$$\pi_s > \tau,$$

with $\tau \in (0, 1)$ a policy threshold. The mapping between τ and the scale of S is made transparent by numerically inverting the fitted mixture to find the cutpoint(s) s^* solving $\Pr(\text{non–compliant} \mid S = s^*) = \tau$; these values are reported to aid auditability. Because S is bounded, we evaluate the posterior on a fine grid over $[0, 1]$ to obtain stable cuts.

Several design choices enhance identification and interpretability. First, the permutation reference distribution is constructed *within school*, so $S_s^{(v)}$ contrasts the observed allocation to the school’s own feasible allocations, not to a cross–school benchmark. Second, eligibility requires at least two classes per school, as concentration is undefined with a single classroom; schools failing this minimum are labeled compliant and flagged via a dedicated indicator to preserve sample coverage without contaminating the mixture. Third, measurement noise is attenuated by scaling inputs, clamping outputs away from the boundaries, and, when plotting diagnostics, averaging across the two subjects to smooth subject–specific idiosyncrasies. Finally, all intermediate objects are saved to disk (separate files for each variable and the combined classification), enabling reproducibility, efficient restarts, and external validation.

The algorithm yields three families of outputs. At the school level we provide $S_s^{(\text{test5})}$,

$S_s^{(\text{escs})}$, and S_s^{comb} alongside the posterior probability π_s and the hard classification, together with the number of classes and a singleton flag. At the distributional level we report fitted mixture parameters and BIC comparisons for alternative k , as well as the implied decision cut(s) s^* for the chosen τ . At the graphical level we supply histograms of S with decision cuts superimposed, facilitating visual inspection of separation between putative compliant and non-compliant groups. In substantive terms, values of S near 0.5 are consistent with random allocation, values approaching 1 indicate concentration that rarely arises by chance, and the posterior π_s quantifies this evidence on a probability scale tied to the observed cross-school distribution. The resulting classification is thus grounded in a design-based comparison (permutation within school) and a model-based calibration (mixture across schools), balancing robustness and interpretability for policy use.